

WP1 - Strengthening AF and carbon farming policies: tools for policymakers

AF-LPIS spatial policy models implemented for use in LL: The *LPIS Sustainability Compass*

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1. Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors groups that are targeted by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners, forest owners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for the first two stakeholders’ groups. It focuses on information collected from farmers in each Member State through the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS): consisting of parcel and sub-parcel boundaries in the Geospatial aid application (GSAA), details on land use, crops and animals in the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS), and data on ground verification from the Area Monitoring Services ([AMS](#)).

This data, already collected from farmers' declarations and other data sources, is not always available in a convenient form for farmers, who often lack the necessary IT skills to overlay several sources of information to extract information relevant to their farm. Additionally, the data resides in different repositories, sometimes with different formats, for different countries. Therefore it is not possible for policy-makers to query the data from different countries easily, e.g. to compare the impact of policy measures across different countries. Finally, given the specific focus of the DigitAF project on agroforestry, we targeted data relevant to the evaluation of the effect of agroforestry adoption on sustainability indicators, which might be different from "standard" agricultural indicators.

This deliverable presents the «LPIS Sustainability Compass», an online spatial tool that provides a focal point to available LPIS data, provided via Web Feature Service (WFS), integrated with Copernicus data (provided via its API) while delivering seamless, on the fly, calculated statistical insights from these datasets related to the selected LPIS plot/farm data, and providing unique contextual data about other plots/farms in the neighborhood from Copernicus services.

This information can be linked to the spatial agroforestry models being developed in the DigitAF project, and in other initiatives. It will facilitate upscaling of results from parcels and farms to catchment and local-government scales and could contribute to the "On-farm Sustainability Compass" advocated in the recent DGAGRI "Vision for Agriculture and Food" (Box 1). This deliverable also provides a focal point for task Task 1.5, which will further integrate environmental and economic apps with the LPIS (Box 2).

BOX 1. The "On-farm Sustainability Compass" announced in the DG AGRI "Vision for Agriculture and Food" ([19.2.2025](#))

*The sustainability compass should act as a one-stop-shop that streamlines reporting and reduces administrative burdens for farmers, **allowing them to monitor and record sustainability data only once**. It will support farmers in gradually **adopting more sustainable practices and attracting new sources of financing**. It will allow them to better measure and benchmark their sustainability performance and demonstrate their provision of ecosystem services through easier data sharing. Improved measurement and reporting can help design public policies in a proportionate way. This voluntary system for **on-farm sustainability assessments** will be developed based on a bottom-up, participatory and 'customer-driven' approach.*

BOX 2 Task 1.5 "Integrating DigitAF Environmental and Economic Apps with the LPIS"

Agronomic (WP2) and economic (WP3) models will be linked to GSAA/LPIS GIS data for parcels in Living Labs and surrounding areas, allowing a range of policy incentives to be evaluated, including for "tree landscape features" (CAP - GAEC8). The models will include environmental, economic and carbon impacts. MVARC and CRAN will provide a GIS environment to visualise present tree cover, and land use, and to evaluate the potential impact of future policy incentives.

The main deliverable from this Task (D1.4) is titled "Agroforestry-LPIS spatial policy models implemented for use in Living Labs"

Member States were obliged by the INSPIRE Directive ([2007/2](#)) to make geospatial data collected with public funds available through their INSPIRE portals¹. However, almost 20 years after entry into

¹ or other recognised geoportals such as the EU [HVD Data Portal](#) or the DGAGRI [Geoportal](#).

force of the Directive, many countries have provided little data in these portals, including the CAP-GSAA-LPIS data needed by DigitAF (see DigitAF [Milestone 6](#)). The Open Data Directive (2019/1024) and its Implementing Regulation (2023/138) confirmed that both GSAA and LPIS data are “high-value” datasets, which must be made available through INSPIRE portals. The latest Implementing Regulation became law on 9.2.23, and MS were allowed 16 months to ensure full compliance. **This period ran out on 9.6.24, but there are 8 Member States (BG, CY, DE, IT, HU, MT, PL, RO) which do not fully provide GSAA-LPIS data, and a number of additional countries where an API is not available.**²

2 Overview of the technical implementation of the «LPIS Sustainability Compass» within the LUCIM web-app

Maintaining the DigitAF project's commitment to the [FAIR](#) principles (GO FAIR, 2025), and in particular the Reusability concept, this Deliverable was implemented by adding a module to the Land Use Change Interactive Map (LUCIM) tool (Tomás et al. 2024b, Palma et al 2024), developed in the AGROMIX Horizon Europe project (2020-2024 GA 862993).

The LUCIM tool aimed to provide broader spatial contexts where agroforestry (AF) could be implemented to increase the environmental resilience of agricultural systems and provide effective climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies. This was achieved through a two-pronged approach described by Palma et al. (2024) with: a) a spatially explicit approach component identifying target regions in Europe where resilient and climate-smart AF systems should have high priority for introduction and b) a non-spatial approach to develop future scenarios of land use/resilience strategies where different models of land use change are evaluated as pathways towards increased resilience to climate change. LUCIM currently runs in MVARC server: https://mvarc.eu/tools/dev/agromix_lucim which is feeding the agromix project website through an iframe @ <https://agromixproject.eu/tools/agromix-land-use-change-interactive-map>.

Since the planned work shares similar goals - namely, the promotion of agroforestry systems by leveraging existing spatial capabilities, data, and models - incorporating these developments into an already established and actively maintained tool was a logical and efficient pathway.

Technically, the LUCIM tool was implemented as a Javascript/HTML/CSS web-app, running entirely in the end user's browser without collecting or storing any personal data. The main libraries used were VueJS³ and Bootstrap⁴ for the web interface and the Eurostat libraries [eurostat-map.js](#)⁵, [gridtiler](#)⁶, and [gridviz](#)⁷ for map generation, being fully open access without the need to register to use. This architecture makes LUCIM a serverless, lightweight, registerless, and operating system-independent tool, an approach that was maintained in the new modules developed in this deliverable for the DigitAF project.

² *The Commission relies on stakeholder complaints from data users who find that a specific High Value Dataset is **not available, not free, not in the correct format, or not accessible via an API as required**. Member States were also required to submit a report to the Commission, by February 9 2025, on the measures they have taken to implement the Regulation. This reporting requirement is additional to the commitment to make the datasets available. EURAF will seek to obtain copies of any such reports relating to GSAA-LPIS data.*

³ <https://vuejs.org/>

⁴ <https://getbootstrap.com/>

⁵ <https://github.com/eurostat/eurostat-map.js>

⁶ <https://github.com/eurostat/gridtiler>

⁷ <https://github.com/eurostat/gridviz>

The code for the «LPIS Sustainability Compass» is publicly available and open to contributions on GitHub at <https://github.com/MVagroecology/lucim>. The tool can be accessed and tested through its web interface at <https://mvagroecology.github.io/lucim> and will be updated with feedback from the living labs where the tool is to be tested, as well as further developments suggested by stakeholders. After improvements following Living Lab feedback, the tool will be made available on DigitAF's website through an iframe, in the same way as the Agromix website, and the code transferred and maintained within EURAF's official repository.

The «LPIS Sustainability Compass» (Figure 1) is designed to function as an online GIS-based environment that aggregates spatial information from datasets conforming to the latest INSPIRE Metadata Technical Guidelines (2023) and which can generate policy-related insights for farmers.

Tranchina et al. (2024), through engagement with farmers involved in the DigitAF Living Labs, highlighted the need for more accessible, transparent, and agroforestry-relevant data systems. They noted that both farmers and policymakers are calling for improvements in LPIS usability, better recording of landscape features, and clearer identification of agroforestry areas. The «LPIS Sustainability Compass» aims to answer these concerns by including parcel data, visualising tree elements provided by Copernicus, and opening opportunities to integrate other Copernicus (<https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products>), EEA (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub>) and other datasets in the High Value Datasets Implementing Regulation (European Union May 2024)⁸. The tool leverages publicly available Geospatial Aid Application (GSAA) and Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) data for parcels located within and around the DigitAF Living Labs.

Figure 1 – «LPIS Sustainability Compass» within the Land Use Change Interactive Mapping (LUCIM), currently available @ <https://mvarc.eu/tools/dev/lucim/>. Note 2 buttons for 1) submitting feedback, 2) loading a sequence that demonstrates the tool capabilities

⁸ See also “step by step guide to accessing High Value Datasets” ([EU Commission 2024](https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/step-by-step-guide-to-accessing-high-value-datasets)).

2.1 Web mapping through OpenLayers

The web GIS-based environment was developed through the open-source Javascript library OpenLayers⁹. This library enables the creation of dynamic, interactive maps and supports the display of map tiles, vector data and markers from a wide range of sources.

2.2 GIS data

The base data for the analysis is sourced from the LPIS system, provided through Web Feature Service (WFS) public URLs. Data such as farm location, parcel boundaries, land use, and crop types are amongst the key elements made available and are essential for further analysis. DigitAF, particularly within Milestone 6 – Availability of LPIS data (Lawson et al. 2025), has made an effort to consistently gather and highlight good practices among national initiatives that aim to make these systems publicly accessible, in line with the INSPIRE Directive, making the case for its increased openness by all Member States - with coordinated coding of crops, land uses and environmental designations. This will ultimately contribute to the development of a FAIRness scoring system for LPIS datasets (see 3.1). Unfortunately, there are still several steps to be taken - while some countries lead with highly accessible and data-rich datasets, others have yet to implement the directive at all.

At the date of this report, all data is loaded through web geo-services such as WFS, WMS (Web Map Service for image data), and XYZ Tiles (for tiled raster images). This approach offers several advantages, e.g. no data needs to be stored locally nor on the app server, avoiding server storage limitations and maintenance overhead. Furthermore, it ensures that users have access to the most up-to-date data available from the source.

A drawback of the tool is its dependence on the reliability of external data endpoints. Any changes or interruptions on these services can potentially break map layers, disrupt analyses, or cause calculation errors. To mitigate these risks, the system continuously monitors endpoint availability through regular pings and implements redundancy by sourcing some data layers from multiple datasets. This balance helps maintain reliability while benefiting from the flexibility of real-time data access.

Through this approach, any dataset made available via web geo-services can be integrated and used within the «LPIS Sustainability Compass». The tool can incorporate several datasets from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service¹⁰ portfolio, and currently showing Tree Cover Density at 10m resolution (table 1). Additional datasets under consideration include those identified in Deliverable 1.2 - Database of Agri-Environmental Indices (Kay et al. 2024), as well as those listed in Deliverables 4.3 (den Herder et al. 2024) and 4.5 (Tomás et al. 2024a) - Data Catalogue.¹¹

Table 1: Datasets included in the «LPIS Sustainability Compass» as of June 2025

Data layer	Source for spatial data web service	Relevance
LPIS - Czech Republic - 2024 - Reference Parcels	https://gis.cenia.cz/geoserver/mze_lpis/wfs "mze_lpis:referenceparcel"	Allows selection of all parcels within a farm; allows for statistical analysis

⁹ <https://openlayers.org/>

¹⁰ <https://land.copernicus.eu/>

¹¹ <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/data>

LPIS - Czech Republic - 2024 - Agricultural Areas	https://gis.cenia.cz/geoserver/mze_lpis/wfs "mze_lpis:agriculturalarea"	at other spatial scales (such as bounding areas or NUTS3 and NUTS4 regions)
LPIS - Czech Republic - 2024 - Ecological Focus Areas	https://gis.cenia.cz/geoserver/mze_lpis/wfs "mze_lpis:ecologicalfocusarea"	
LPIS - Portugal - 2024 Reference parcels	https://www.ifap.pt/isip/ows/isip.data/wfs "isip.data:parcelas.2024jun10"	
LPIS - Portugal - 2024 Land cover	https://www.ifap.pt/isip/ows/isip.data/wfs "isip.data:ocupacoes.solo.2024jun10"	
Tree Cover Density (10 m resolution) - 2021 - Copernicus	https://geoserver.vlcc.geoville.com/geoserver/ows	Allows computing the % of tree cover per parcel and per farm (several parcels selected)
Corine Land cover 2018 (100 m resolution)	https://image.discomap.eea.europa.eu/arcgis/services/Corine/CLC2018_WM/MapServer/WMSServer?service=WMS&request=GetCapabilities&version=1.3.0	Allows to identify Agroforestry class (244) and contribute to identify classification problems
Grassland 2021 (10-100 m resolution)	https://geoserver.vlcc.geoville.com/geoserver/ows?service=WMS&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities	Allows to identify grassland within AF parcels
JRC Global forest cover 2020	https://ies-ows.jrc.ec.europa.eu/iforce/gfc2020/wms.py	Allows to check for EU Deforestation (EUDR) (2023/1115) compliance

In the near future, the use of individual national LPIS datasets may be replaced by the LPIS Aggregator¹², a tool currently under development within DigitAF that aggregates LPIS data from multiple EU Member States into a unified platform, allowing users to inspect parcel-level information such as area, land use, and crop codes. The LPIS Aggregator aims to evolve into a single, long-term web service that works over stable and permanent LPIS datasets. Ongoing efforts include clarifying licensing conditions with Member States, aligning with INSPIRE Directive requirements, and developing an API for streamlined data access. While this important and ambitious aggregator is ongoing, a country-by-country basis is implemented in the «LPIS sustainability compass» depending on the current effort of each country to implement the INSPIRE directive and make LPIS available as WFS/WMS services. Legacy data handling and interoperability with other initiatives such as EURO-Crops¹³ are also under active consideration.

2.3 Geospatial analysis with Turf.js

With the web GIS environment established and data organized across multiple layers, the next step is to perform geospatial analysis to extract meaningful insights for farmers. This is achieved using the

¹² <https://maps.regenfarmer.com/>

¹³ <https://github.com/maja601/EuroCrops>

open-source JavaScript library Turf.js¹⁴, which offers a range of spatial operations, utility functions for generating GeoJSON data, as well as tools for data classification and statistical analysis.

Parcel-level analysis is currently supported (e.g. calculating Tree Cover Density per parcel and per farm), and additional spatial aggregation levels - such as bounding areas or NUTS3 and NUTS4 regions - are under consideration, provided that computational and data loading requirements remain within manageable limits for computing within the user's browser.

3 Examples of spatial insights into a Parcel or Farm provided by the «LPIS Sustainability Compass»

The following are some examples of use cases that the «LPIS Sustainability Compass» is designed to support.

3.1 How representative is the parcel/farm compared to its surrounding area?

Compare the land use (e.g. of Living Lab parcel/farms) to that of surrounding areas, providing insights into their representativeness within broader landscapes. This comparison is made within various spatial scales, such as NUTS3 or NUTS4 administrative regions, or a fixed e.g. 10 × 10 km bounding box (editable bounding box size) - an approach particularly relevant for establishing standardized baselines. In addition to land use, agro-environmental indices calculated at the farm level will also be compared to those of the surrounding area. This functionality aims to contextualize farm performance and support more informed policy and management decisions.

3.2 Land use classification challenges

Accurate land use classification is crucial for policy compliance and sustainability monitoring. However, discrepancies often arise between different datasets. For instance, the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) (2023/1115), effective from 30 December 2025, mandates that certain commodities, such as cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, soya, wood, and rubber, must be proven to be deforestation-free and legally produced to be placed on the EU market or exported. A critical component of this regulation is the use of geospatial data to verify compliance. To support this, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) developed the Global Forest Cover (GFC) 2020 dataset, which provides a spatially explicit representation of forest presence and absence for the year 2020 at a 10m resolution. This dataset is integral to the EUDR's risk assessment framework, aiding in the identification of areas where deforestation has occurred since the cut-off date of 31 December 2020.

Key questions arise around the degree of concordance between this forest cover dataset, with information on agricultural and forestry land use information available from the LPIS: what types of discrepancies exist, at what spatial scales, and between which specific land uses? In particular, agricultural areas with tree cover, such as certain types of permanent crops, pastures with scattered trees, or agroforestry systems, are frequently misclassified as "forest" in global datasets like the one from the JRC. This misalignment can lead to major policy and compliance challenges (see [EURAF Policy Briefing #15](#)).

Understanding these discrepancies is vital for farmers. Misclassifications could impact eligibility for subsidies or support under this and multiple other EU policies. By being aware of how their land is classified, farmers can better navigate regulatory requirements and ensure compliance, thereby safeguarding their access to financial support and avoiding potential penalties.

¹⁴ <https://turfjs.org/>

The «LPIS Sustainability Compass» offers a platform to explore and address the complex challenges of land use classification, enabling stakeholders to share their perspectives through their specific contextual lenses. It also provides a channel to visualize statutory land use constraints, physical limitations to land use change, and opportunities for tree planting, all within a tool that can be integrated with other DigitAF socio-economic and biophysical models.

3.3 Identifying tree-rich and tree-poor farms

Using satellite-based tree cover density data, such as the Copernicus Tree Cover Density (TCD) layers, it is possible to identify “tree desert” areas within agricultural land or even Trees Outside Forests (TOF). By overlaying this information with LPIS parcel data, specific patterns emerge, showing where tree presence in farmland is high (e.g. agroforestry systems) or nearly absent. The TCD dataset also enables tree density to be assessed at the parcel level, helping to classify farmland into categories such as grassland with trees or silvoarable systems based on thresholds (e.g. >5% or >10% TCD).

These insights are valuable for farmers by helping them understand how their land compares to regional tree cover baselines, identify opportunities for agroforestry expansion, and align with climate and biodiversity targets. Use of GSAA-LPIS parcel codes is specifically recommended in the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation ([2024/3012](#)) and in monitoring of landscape features needed for compliance with the Nature Restoration Regulation (Commission Notice [C/2025/980](#) 14.2.2025), and with CAP Conditionality requirements.

3.4 Recording conditionality within other legal designations at parcel or sub-parcel scale

The geospatial implications for “conditionality” in the CAP are summarised in Annex III of the Strategic Plan Regulation (2021/2115) and require monitoring by CAP Managing Authorities, and compliance by farmers. The «LPIS Sustainability Compass» is being developed to deliver the following indicators at plot or farm level:

Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC)

- GAEC1 - Maintenance of permanent grassland based on a ratio of permanent grassland in relation to agricultural area at national, regional, subregional, group-of-holdings or holding level in comparison to the reference year 2018, with a maximum decrease of 5 % allowed.
- GAEC2 - Protection of wetland and peatland soils, where whole parcels or parts of parcels are designated as susceptible to constraints on the type of land use and ploughing allowed
- GAEC3 - Ban on the burning of arable stubble - except for plant health reasons - tracked using the Area Monitoring System.
- GAEC4 - Establishment of buffer strips along water courses - involving preservation of a 3m strip along watercourses, which should be mapped. Additional funding may be available for planting new herbaceous or woody strips.
- GAEC5 - Tillage management to reduce the risk of soil degradation and erosion, including consideration of the slope gradient - which may involve mapping of erosion risk at parcel or sub parcel scale.
- GAEC6 - Minimum soil cover to avoid bare soil in periods that are most sensitive - with rules set by Member States and monitoring through the Area Monitoring Service.
- GAEC7 - Crop rotation in arable land, except for crops growing under water - where LPIS data is used to establish sufficient rotations ([Bergkvist et al 2023](#)) and compliance is monitored through the Copernicus Area Monitoring Service.

- GAEC8 - Minimum area devoted to landscape features (hedges, trees, ponds, terraces, copses etc) and non-productive areas (fallow land) - this requirement was removed in the simplification package of 14.5.2024 ([2024/1468](#)), but Management Agencies are still required to monitor the retention of landscape features by farmers.
- GAEC9 - Ban on converting or ploughing permanent grassland designated at environmentally-sensitive permanent grasslands in Natura 2000 sites.

Statutory Monitoring Requirements

- SMR1 - Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC) monitoring - particularly diffuse sources of pollution by phosphates
- SMR2 - Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) - protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources.
- SMR3 - Wild Birds Directive (91/676/EEC) - conservation of wild birds.
- SMR4 - Habitats Directive - conservation of natural habitats and wild flora and fauna, and mainly represented by Natura 2000 habitat designations

Furthermore, a range of agri-environmental indicators could be calculated at parcel and farm scale using methodologies developed for the CAP Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework. These are discussed in DigitAF Deliverable 1.2 ([Kay et al 2024](#)). Other examples of use cases are given in DigitAF Policy Briefing #68.

4 Future work

4.1 FAIRness scoring system for LPIS datasets

As part of the DigitAF project's commitment to the FAIR data principles, and following previously created FAIRness scores for tools and datasets (Tomás et al, 2024b), a new scoring system is being developed to assess the FAIRness of national LPIS datasets across EU Member States. This system will evaluate key criteria such as data discoverability, licensing clarity, technical accessibility (e.g. via web services such as WFS/WMS), metadata quality, spatial resolution, and number of available years. The goal is to provide a transparent benchmark dashboard of how well each LPIS dataset supports open science and digital innovation in agriculture. For both policymakers and data users, including farmers and advisors, this scoring system will offer a practical guide to understanding where gaps remain in data availability and how national systems align with EU directives like INSPIRE.

4.2 Translating and "spatialising" CAP policy

To bridge the gap between policy and practical application, particularly within the CAP, DigitAF is working to translate complex policy rules into structured, spatially explicit data that can be directly used alongside LPIS parcel information. This process includes decoding eligibility criteria, identifying eco-scheme requirements, and linking policy conditions to mapped land use. By integrating policy logic with real-world parcel data, the system will enable farmers to better understand compliance thresholds, identify opportunities for support, and make informed land management decisions aligned with CAP objectives.

4.3 Evaluate the impact of agroforestry adoption

Linking the «LPIS sustainability compass» with spatial agroforestry models being developed in the DigitAF project will allow ex ante evaluation of the potential impact of increasing tree cover (e.g. by adopting agroforestry practices such as hedgerows, riparian buffers, silvoarable or silvopastoral

trees) on a range of sustainability indicators. These include, among others, evaluating the impact of increasing tree cover on carbon storage, biodiversity and soil health.

4.4 Living Labs feedback

The DigitAF project will expose the «LPIS Sustainability Compass» in the Living Labs where feedback will be explored to assess usability and usefulness. The exposure to different lenses of stakeholders will widen critical capacity and enable them to explore the potential of the online tool. Important feedback is expected from the Living Labs and other stakeholders. On one hand, what can be done within the DigitAF project to improve the tool in terms of usability and usefulness, for example which already available datasets through WFS can be implemented straightaway (to improve usefulness) and, on the other hand, create a wishlist (e.g. datasets that might not be available publicly) to envision further evaluations and assessments, either at parcel/farm and policy level, and encourage data curators to make the data available.

4.5 Future Policy Demands

The Soil Monitoring Directive, Forest Monitoring Regulation, Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Regulation, Nature Restoration Regulation and the recent Water Resilience Strategy ([4.6.2025](#)) all have monitoring requirements which could, eventually, integrate with the «LPIS Sustainability Compass». The necessity to comply with these directives could be a strong incentive to ensure that all Member States (and regions) become compliant with the INSPIRE Directive and the High Value Datasets Regulation.

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5.1 Note on Copernicus API and other open-access data

This deliverable heavily relies on open-access and open-source, for both software and data. It is therefore in line with the INSPIRE Directive¹⁵ (almost 20 years old) as well as the younger (5 years old) Open Data Directive¹⁶. We salute the development and the openness of the Copernicus project, especially their API development, as well as other open-access bodies either governmental and non-governmental, that are engaging with the FAIR principles¹⁷. The pursuit of such ideals and strategies enabled us to accomplish our goals while expanding our vision beyond the original scope, allowing us to develop new applications not foreseen by the initial data providers, yet potentially valuable in advancing more sustainable farming practices.

¹⁵ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/oj>

¹⁶ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>

¹⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

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